

A STUDY ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR TOWARDS E-MARKETING IN TRICHY

Dr. Xavier Amaladoss* & M. Manimaran**

* Professor in Management, Srinivasan College of Arts & Science,
Perambalur, Tamil Nadu

** Assistant Professor in Management, Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College,
Perambalur, Tamil Nadu

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Abstract:

E-Marketing can be defined as marketing of products and services on electronic media .E-Marketing is one of the latest and emerging tools in the marketing world .It include the creative use of internet technology including use of various multimedia ,graphics ,text etc .with different languages to create catchy advertisements ,forms ,e-shop where product can be viewed ,promoted and sold .It includes advertisement (flash , text, graphics ,audio or video), product display ,product navigation,3-D products view ,basket selection, checkout and payment E-marketing and internet marketing terms are used in the same sense. This form of marketing is equally applicable in most of the business models:

- E-commerce - Direct sales of good to the mass customer/consumer or the business customers.
- Publishing services-where advertisements are sold.
- Lead-based websites - like policy bazaar, Sulekha where sales leads are generated are sold to either third party or used in-house to convert them into sales through appropriate channel.
- Affiliate marketing - a referral marketing strategy where reward is given for referring product, company, or website to other friends, relative or in nutshell other potential customer or target segment.

Objectives of the Study:

- To analyze the awareness of e-marketing among the people in Trichy.
- To realize the impact of e-marketing on purchase decision of consumers.
- Identify the relationship of demographical factors that influence online shopping.
- To determine the factors affecting the perception of online buyers.

Statement of the Problem:

In the case of online marketing, there is no direct personal meet of the marketers and consumers. Hence, the marketers have to be careful in the determination of the customers' expectations and perception on various aspects related to the products and services in online marketing. They should be aware of the factors leading to their attitude towards online marketing. At the same time; the marketers should know their strengths and weakness in online marketing. If not, there will be a lot of services failure. Nowadays, the handling of service failure in online marketing has received increasing attention. The online marketing is subjected to some issues like credit card security, privacy, on-time delivery and ease of navigation

Research Methodology of the Study:

Sample Design:

A sample design is a definite plan for obtaining a sample from a given population. It refers to the technique to the procedure adopted in selecting items for the sampling designs are as below:

Sample Size:

The substantial portions of the target customers that are sampled to achieve reliable result are 85.

Sampling Method:

Non probability sampling method: Convenient sampling.

Data Collection:

The study was conducted by the means of personal interview with respondents and the information given by they were directly recorded on questionnaire. For the purpose of analyzing the data it is necessary to collect the vital information. There are two types of data, they are

- Primary data
- Secondary data

Collection Techniques:

- Primary Data: Primary data will be conducted through questionnaire.
- Secondary Data: Secondary data will be collected through books, journals and various websites

Review of Literature:

- Sharma, Gupta and Manhas (2002) in one of the article entitled -"Internet marketing: opportunities and challenges" found that internet marketing will add a new dimensions to the concept of marketing. Due to the concept of internet marketing, there is practically no geographical bar for the company .E-

shopping is one such marketing service which is available to the customer uninterrupted 24 hours a day and 7 days a week.

- Ahuja, Gupta and Raman (2003) conducted the study entitled - “An Empirical Investigation of Online Consumer Purchasing Behavior” and the study found that 4% of people gave -inability to touch and feel the product as a reason -for not shopping online.
- Dr. Durmaz (2011) in the study entitled-“Impact of cultural factors on online shopping behavior” and the study found that while buying goods and services ,cultures, beliefs and traditional take an important position ,while the environment, friends and social groups stated 48.6%.In this case the impact of cultural factors means a lot.

Weighted Ranking Method:

Table 1: Main Reason for Online Shopping

Category	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total	Ranking
Price	145	104	63	14	2	328	1
Convenience and Time Saving	80	120	84	10	4	298	5
Fast Shipping	115	120	69	10	4	318	3
Security	75	104	72	36	2	289	6
Brand Conscious	85	136	69	16	3	308	4
Attractive Offers	115	104	87	2	1	319	2

Source: Primary data

Interpretation:

Main reason for online shopping is ranked are as follows:

- Price is ranked 1st by the respondents.
- Attractive offers is ranked 2nd by the respondents.
- Fast shipping is ranked 3rd by the respondents.
- Brand conscious is ranked 4th by the respondents.
- Convenience and time saving is ranked 5th by the respondents.
- Security is ranked 6th by the respondents.

Table 2: Income of the Respondents and Modes of Payments

Income	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig.
Credit Card	15	3.20	1.207	.734	.572
Debit Card	16	2.81	1.223		
Online Banking Transaction	6	2.83	1.329		
Cash On Delivery	46	2.91	.985		
Others	2	4.0	1.414		
Total	85	2.64	1.096		

Source: Primary data

P-value: .572

The above table no. 4.36 shows that the modes of payment at different income levels. It was found that though there were differences in modes of payments among income level. There is no statistical significant difference among behaviors income levels. Thus, no relationship was found between income level and modes of payments in this study.

Result:

Hence, the P-value is greater than 0.05, the relationship between the income level of the respondents and the modes of payments are not significant.

So, the null hypothesis is applicable.

H0: There is no significant difference between age and feeling secure while shopping online.

Ha: There is significant difference between gender and feelings secure while shopping online.

Chi-Square Test:

Table 3: Qualification of the Respondents and How the Respondents Know the Shopping Websites Crosstab

Qualification	With the Recommendation of Friend	With the Advertisement in Press And Media	With the Search Engines	With Links	Others	Total
High School	7	2	1	0	1	11
Bachelor Degree	8	5	4	5	2	24
Master Degree	20	9	6	5	2	42
Ph.D. Degree	3	3	1	1	0	8
Total	38	19	12	11	5	85

Chi-Square Test:

	Value	df	Asymp.sig (2-sifded)
Pearson Chi-Square	6.632	12	.881

Source: Primary data

Chi-square value : 6.632

Degree of freedom : 12

P-Value : .881

Result:

Hence, the P-value is greater than 0.05, the relationship between gender of the respondents and the internet accesses the most are not significant.

So, the null hypothesis is applicable.

H0: There is no significant difference between age and feelings secure while shopping online.

Ha: There is significant difference between gender and feelings secure while shopping online.

Table 4: Age of the Respondents and Feeling Secure While Ahopping Online

Age	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	F	Sig
Yes	62	2.65	1.010	.022	.883
No	23	2.61	1.033		
Total	85	2.64	1.010		

Source: Primary data

P-value: .883

The above table no.4.35 shows that the feeling secure while shopping online by different age groups. It was found that though there was difference in security among the age groups. There is no statistical significant difference among various age groups.

Thus, no relationship was found between age and security while shopping online in this study.

Result:

Hence, the P-value is greater than 0.05, the relationship between age groups of the respondents and the hours spent on the internet are not significant.

Findings and Suggestions:

- Online shopping is growing bigger and more popular each passing day .It gives you the ability to search for the products you like in a flash from the comfort of your home and availability of 24*7.It is convenient and time saving.
- Almost all the people are aware of the online shopping .The prime motive for surfing the net remains remain checking the products before to buy. The reason being the issues concerning the security of the credit cards.
- The promotional strategies and methods do influence and motivate the buyer towards online shopping. These promotional strategies create excitement about the brands and entice the consumer to visit a shopping site.
- Many consumers who buy online for the sake of convenience have not had very pleasant experiences. There are too many cases of delayed delivery, damaged goods, quality issues and even instances of cheating where the goods are shipped.
- Most of the people feel that products available through online shopping are costly because of the shipping charges whereas in the traditional shopping there are no such charges. So the companies should provide the facility of free delivery in order to create excitement among non-users.
- Websites should be made more attractive and appealing to the buyer in order to retain the potential shoppers. Moreover, the sellers should ensure that the shopper easily and quickly gets to the final shopping-cart web page, instead of undergoing a series of clicks from one webpage to another.

Suggestions of the Study:

- Online stores should use effective implementation of websites factors such as information design, features, communication, privacy and security, as a marketing stool by which trust towards the website can be created among the consumers and subsequently enhance purchase intention.
- People are aware to online shopping because there is a difficulty in returning the faulty products. Hence the companies should make the arrangement so that try and buy facility is available at the customer doorstep and one can return if the product is faulty.
- One of the most reasons for not doing online shopping is that there is a less chance of making reasonable negotiations and bargaining .It has been found that Indian consumers are price sensitive. Hence the price sensitive consumers do not take much interest in online shopping. So the companies should allow considerable bargain for the customers.

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